

Identification of gaps, redundancies, and possible synergies regarding different user journeys of researchers in EHDS and EOSC

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Executive Summary

The Health Data Task Force is dedicated to harmonizing and cultivating synergies between the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) and the European Health Data Space (EHDS) and helping shape strategy for EOSC on how to engage with the health data ecosystem in general. This commitment encompasses, notably, the minimisation of redundancies between the two initiatives and the collaborative development of shared elements such as interoperability and the exchange of health data and services between EHDS and other related activities within EOSC, or the utilization of EOSC as a provider of resources (including storage, computational capacities, and other pertinent infrastructure solutions) for EHDS. Both EHDS and EOSC face common challenges in ensuring data adheres to Open Science, FAIR, and in particular FAIR-Health principles¹, with particular emphasis in this context on discoverability, interoperability (specifically, semantic interoperability within an international context), data quality, and privacy protection mechanisms that effectively balance data accessibility and utility with the privacy of data subjects.

This document presents an initial gap analysis of the interplay between the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) ecosystem and the European Health Data Space (EHDS) regulation, with the aim of identifying differences, overlaps, and potential synergies. It explores how EHDS regulations impact health data access and use for research, assesses the alignment of the HealthData@EU infrastructure with open science principles, and identifies opportunities to enhance transparency, collaboration, and reproducibility in European health and biomedical research. The analysis covers three key areas: (1) stakeholders, examining gaps, redundancies, and opportunities, as well as possible synergies among involved actors; (2) interoperability, identifying technical and organizational gaps and areas of alignment; and (3) a synthesis of synergies and opportunities for strategic convergence between EOSC and EHDS. This initial assessment lays the groundwork for future alignment and coordination between these two major European data initiatives.

The document is structured into four main parts: **Introduction**, which sets out the EOSC, EHDS, HealthData@EU, their respective approaches, and the European Interoperability Framework; **Mapping the Existing Landscape**, which reviews stakeholders and existing mechanisms for health data sharing and use; and three analytical chapters—**Data Hosting, Discoverability and Accessibility**, **(Data) Interoperability and Quality**, and **Data Processing**—which each examine the current landscape, identify gaps and redundancies, and highlight opportunities for synergies between EHDS and EOSC.

¹ <https://doi.org/10.1089/bio.2017.0110>

1 Introduction

1.1 European Open Science Cloud

The European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) is a European initiative aimed at providing a virtual, open, and trusted multi-disciplinary environment for researchers and innovators in Europe. Its primary goal is to allow them to publish, find, and reuse research data, tools, and services, thereby promoting open science practices and increasing the productivity, traceability, reproducibility, and trustworthiness of research.

EOSC is not a single, new digital infrastructure, but rather a "system of systems." It aims at federating existing data repositories, research infrastructures, and e-infrastructures across Europe, creating a network of "nodes" that are interconnected. This approach leverages existing investments and promotes the interoperability of data across different disciplines, adhering to the FAIR principles² (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable).

Even though it is not a legal instrument (regulation nor directive) nor is being directly supported by any European legal instrument, the EOSC is recognised as the common European research and innovation data space and a key action of the European Research Area (ERA) policy agenda, providing technical and organisational support for Open Science. It is important to note that EOSC might involve support of data and sectors which are regulated by other sectoral legal instruments; including in the health data domain, where an example of such regulation is European Health Data Space Regulation (EHDS).

The technical and organisational support is now being materialised in the building of the EOSC Federation, composed of a network of EOSC Nodes which include institutional, regional, national, and European data repositories, research infrastructures, e-infrastructures, and other scientific service providers. An EOSC Node can be a single organization or a consortium of organizations, each providing resources and services to the Federation.

An EOSC Node is an organisation or a network of organisations that provide and manage scientific data, knowledge, and resources. These services are referred to as "Federating Capabilities". The services an EOSC Node provides can be either created by the Node itself, by members of its community, or by third-party providers. The EOSC Federation Handbook (second edition released early 2026) is a comprehensive, practical guide designed for organizations joining the EOSC Federation³.

The services are broadly classified as follows⁴:

- EOSC Federating Capabilities: These are services provided by one or more EOSC Nodes for common or cross-node functions of the EOSC Federation. These capabilities are specified in the EOSC Federation Handbook and as of November 2025, they can be either:
 - Mandatory: A subset of Federating Capabilities in which all EOSC Nodes must participate to join the Federation.

² Wilkinson, M., Dumontier, M., Aalbersberg, I. et al. The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship. *Sci Data* 3, 160018 (2016). <https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18>

³ EOSC Federation Handbook, revision version 1, date 27 March 2025. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14999577>

⁴ *ibid*

- Federation Catalogue: Each node must identify a subset of its resources (services, datasets, etc.) to be exposed in the EOSC Federation Catalogue, operated by the EOSC EU Node (Resource Hub).
 - Access to Node Resources via eduGain IdPs: Each node must operate an AARC Blueprint compliant AAI infrastructure and join the eduGAIN Federation as a Service Provider.
 - Recommended/Optional Capabilities. Nodes are encouraged to participate in these capabilities, but it is not a requirement for joining the Federation. Examples include:
 - Professional Operation of Digital Infrastructure: EOSC Nodes are required to have a Service Management System (SMS) in place that complies with standards like FitSM or ISO 20000-1 and is compatible with ITIL (Information Technology Infrastructure Library) best practices.
 - PID Service: A distributed service for storing, managing, and accessing Persistent Identifiers (PIDs). The service offers a REST API and a native Handle API.
 - Compute/Storage: Cloud compute and storage resources to support processing, analytics, and other data- and compute-intensive use cases.
 - Containers: A service that enables the deployment of cloud-native applications for scientific communities.
 - Bulk Data Transfer: A service to manage and transfer large datasets reliably, ensuring data accuracy and integrity.
 - File Sync and Share: A service allowing users to securely share files across multiple devices and with multiple people.
 - Interactive Notebooks: A flexible environment for data scientists and developers to create, run, and share notebooks.
 - Large File Transfer: A service for end-users to transfer large files over the Internet
- Research Resources: These are the services and other assets that are made available within the EOSC Federation. These are further categorised as: Research publications, Research data sources (e.g., FAIR Data repositories, research databases), Research software, Research services (also called Node Generic Capabilities), Research training, Scientific Resource and Service Discovery, etc.
 - Specifically for health data, EHDS is a non-exclusive data access mechanism and hence health data can be shared within EOSC based on other current or future legal instruments (e.g., using one of the available legal bases in GDPR Art. 9 §2 and mechanism of Data Transfer Agreements compliant to GDPR).

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Figure 1: Schema of the interactions among nodes. Bars denote services exposed and circle services being used.

Currently, the EOSC Federation is being built with an initial EOSC EU reference node⁵ and 13 Candidate EOSC Nodes⁶ selected in a competitive call in February 2025.

1.2 European Health Data Space Regulation

For health-related data, EOSC Nodes and their participants must comply with sectoral legislation governing the processing of such data, including the European Health Data Space (EHDS) Regulation. EOSC provides a technical and organisational environment to support open science, while the EHDS establishes the legal framework for the secure and lawful secondary use of electronic health data.

The European Health Data Space (EHDS) is the EU's common framework for the use and exchange of health data. The EHDS Regulation establishes a unified system for accessing and sharing electronic health data across the EU for defined purposes (see below) under European Union law. It was officially published in the Official Journal of the European Union on 5 March 2025 and entered into force on 26 March 2025.

The EHDS addresses both primary and secondary uses of health data.

- Primary use (EHDS Chapter II⁷) refers to individuals' control over their personal health data, including access and sharing for the purpose of healthcare delivery - resulting in MyHealth@EU infrastructure.

⁵ <https://open-science-cloud.ec.europa.eu/>

⁶ <https://eosc.eu/news/eoscs-build-up-phase-to-begin-with-march-kick-off/>

⁷ https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/HTML/?uri=OJ:L_202500327#cpt_II

- Interoperability of Electronic Health Record (EHR) systems and wellness applications (EHDS Chapter III⁸).
- Secondary use (EHDS Chapter IV⁹) involves the secure re-use of health data for research, innovation, policy-making, and regulatory purposes - resulting in HealthData@EU infrastructure.

This document focuses on the user journeys of researchers within the EHDS and EOSC, with particular emphasis on the secondary uses of health data. The secondary use of health data in EHDS is expected to:

- Accelerate medical research,
- Support the development of public health policies,
- Improve healthcare outcomes (e.g. through new treatments and better patient care),
- Identify best practices,
- Enhance transparency and accountability in the healthcare sector.

Timing of the EHDS application of the secondary use provisions: Starting in March 2029,¹⁰ the EHDS provisions regarding secondary use will apply to most categories of health data. Authorised Participants on HealthData@EU¹¹ established under Union law can be onboarded starting from 2029. By March 2031, they will extend to all remaining categories, including genomic data. From March 2035, third countries and international organisations will also be able to participate in the secondary use of health data (Art.75(5)); reciprocal access decisions under Art. 91 can happen earlier, too.

Given the sensitive nature of health data, the EHDS builds on key EU legislation such as the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), the Data Governance Act, the Data Act, and the Network and Information Systems Directive. The EHDS enables secondary use of health data under specific legal bases and safeguards, even where individual consent is not required, ensuring that all processing takes place within a clear legal framework and under the supervision of Health Data Access Bodies. It ensures responsible and secure secondary use through the following measures:

- Data governance:
 - clear rules for data discoverability, access, sharing, and use;
 - decision making by independent Authorisation by Health Data Access Bodies (HDABs);
 - an opt-out mechanism allowing individuals to withdraw their data from secondary use through a simple, transparent, and reversible process.
- Data protection, security, and public trust:

⁸ https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/HTML/?uri=OJ:L_202500327#cpt_III

⁹ https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/HTML/?uri=OJ:L_202500327#cpt_IV

¹⁰ EHDS Art. 105 on entry into force and application

¹¹ EHDS Rec. 80 and Art.75(4)

- responsibility of Health Data Access Bodies (HDABs)
- data minimisation, anonymisation, and pseudonymisation in line with requirements of GDPR;
- data processing is only possible within the Secure Processing Environments (SPEs), from which only non-personal data and anonymised statistical data can be retrieved as a result of the processing.
- EHDS introduces purposes for which processing is strictly prohibited¹², such as:
 - Making decisions that negatively affect individuals or groups
 - Using data for marketing purposes
 - Attempting to re-identify data subjects

The use of anonymised data is mandatory, unless the purposes of processing require the use of personal or pseudonymised, which should be justified for intended purpose—in which case pseudonymised data may be accessed in SPEs.

EOSC supports open science, whereas EHDS governs the lawful secondary use of health data; they are therefore complementary but independent.

1.2.1 Implementation of the EHDS regulation: the HealthData@EU Infrastructure

HealthData@EU is the common European infrastructure established by the European Commission and the Member States under the European Health Data Space (EHDS) Regulation. It facilitates the secure and ethical secondary use of health data across Europe. Other entities established under Union law, such as ERICs or EDICs, may participate in specific roles defined by the Regulation (e.g., as data holders, service providers, or authorised participants). It is a core component of the broader European Health Data Space (EHDS), a new framework designed to empower individuals with more control over their health data while also allowing it to be used for important purposes like research, innovation, and policymaking.

Figure 2 depicts the major components of such infrastructure and their mutual interactions.

- Health Data Holders: These are the entities that collect and store electronic health data as part of their activities. They are the providers of the data. This includes a wide array of organizations, such as hospitals, public health bodies, research institutions, pharmaceutical companies, and even developers of health and wellness apps. Their primary responsibility is to make their data available for secondary use, provided they have a legal obligation to do so.
 - Health Data Intermediation Entities¹³ are legal persons that Member States may designate to carry out the duties of certain categories of health data holders. This is intended to reduce the administrative burden on some data holders, particularly smaller ones.

¹² EHDS Art. 57

¹³EHDS, Recital 59 and Art. 50 §3

- In the case of cross-border registries or databases, such as the registries of European Reference Networks for Rare Diseases, which receive data from different healthcare providers in several Member States, the health data access body of the Member State where the coordinator of the registry is located should be responsible for providing access to data.¹⁴
- Trusted Health Data Holders¹⁵ are specific health data holders designated by a Member State because they meet certain conditions, such as the ability to provide data through a secure processing environment compliant with Article 73 and possession of the necessary expertise to assess data access applications. When a data request solely involves data they hold, they assess the request and provide a proposal for a decision to the HDAB. This creates a simplified procedure for the HDAB to issue a data permit, and subsequently, the trusted holder carries out implementation tasks like preparing the data for secure access. A key distinction is that Health Data Intermediation Entities **cannot** be designated as Trusted Health Data Holders.
- Health Data Users: These are the individuals and organizations that request and process health data for secondary purposes. This group includes researchers, innovators, policymakers, and public health bodies who need access to datasets to advance medical science, develop new technologies, or improve public health strategies. They can issue either data requests¹⁶, where data is processed by the HDAB and only resulting anonymised statistical data is returned to the user, or data access application¹⁷, which—if approved—results in data permit¹⁸ to process the data in an SPE only for the purposes stated in their application.
- Health Data Access Bodies (HDABs): These are the national entities established in each EU Member State. They are the gatekeepers of the data. Their key roles include:
 - Managing dataset catalogues¹⁹ and exposing metadata to the EU-level dataset catalogue operated through the EU Central Platform, in accordance with Article 63(1)(a) and Article 77 of the EHDS Regulation.
 - Reviewing independently and approving or denying applications from Health Data Applicants (who, if the application is approved, become Health Data Users).
 - Managing access to the data, ensuring it is processed in SPEs and managing risks of data to be retrieved from SPEs.
 - Acting as the main point of contact between data users and data holders.
 - Implementing information duty to the public (information portal).
 - Monitoring compliance with the EHDS regulation²⁰.

¹⁴ EHDS Recital 82 and Art.76

¹⁵EHDS, Recital 76 and Art. 72 §2

¹⁶ EHDS, Art. 69

¹⁷ EHDS, Art. 67

¹⁸ EHDS, Art. 68

¹⁹ EHDS, Art. 77 §1

²⁰ EHDS Art. 57 §1(a)(ii)

- EU Central Platform: is the digital hub of the infrastructure, being operated by the EC. It provides the following features:
 - Dataset Catalogue: It hosts a central, searchable catalogue of metadata, allowing data users to discover what datasets are available in different EU countries.
 - Application Hub: It provides a standardised system for users to submit data access applications to the relevant national HDABs (in addition to access application systems provided by HDABs).
 - Cross-Border Facilitation: It connects national HDABs to streamline the process of requesting data from multiple countries.
 - Provide access to an EC SPE for those requests that require data for multiple MSs or from MSs that have not already set up theirs.
- **Authorised Participants:** Research infrastructures that operate under EU law and support the use of electronic health data for research, policy-making, statistics, and regulatory purposes may also apply for authorisation to operate as an authorised participant of the infrastructure provided, they comply with all EHDS obligations (e.g. use within permitted purposes, use of SPEs, reporting). This ensures that large-scale, collaborative research efforts can access the necessary data seamlessly. Applicability of Authorised Participant status is differentiated in the EHDS regulation: entities established under European law (such as ERICs, EDICs or other infrastructures under Union legal acts including EOSC contributors²¹) can request to become Authorised Participants from 2029, while international organisations and third countries starting from 2035.

²¹ EHDS, Rec. 80 - "In addition, authorised participants in HealthData@EU could be research infrastructures established as a European Research Infrastructure Consortium (ERIC) under Council Regulation (EC) No 723/2009 (19), as a European digital infrastructure consortium (EDIC) under Decision (EU) 2022/2481 or similar infrastructures established under other Union legal acts, as well as other types of entities, including infrastructures under the European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures (ESFRI) or infrastructures federated under the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC). Third countries and international organisations could also become authorised participants in HealthData@EU, provided that they are compliant with the requirements in this Regulation."

Cross-border secondary use infrastructure

HealthData@EU

Figure 2: This schematic illustrates different entities in the HealthData@EU infrastructure ecosystem and their mutual interactions (Source: European Commission).

1.3 EHDS and EOSC approaches

On October 8th 2024 members of the EOSC Association, Horizon Europe INFRAEOSC projects and officers of the Digital Health Unit (C.1) from DG Sante had a meeting in Brussels to perform an initial scouting regarding the opportunities on if and how EOSC may support the development of the EHDS regulation. This Section provides a summary of the outcomes of this meeting. A detailed consolidated position document resulting from this meeting is available at [Brussels Round Table on EHDS and EOSC, 8 October 2024](#).

As a European Data Space, EOSC can support the implementation of the EHDS by promoting interoperability and FAIR-by-design standards for relevant research resources, but it does not form part of the EHDS governance or legal framework.

Figure 3: Simplified schematics of user journey in EHDS when using data access application/data permit mechanism. Note that data requesting mechanism is intentionally omitted for the sake of simplicity.

The round table discussions centred on aligning the European Health Data Space (EHDS) and the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) for the secondary use of health data. Following the Health Data User Journey presented in Figure 3, key themes were:

1. **Data discovery:** Strategies for making health data findable across both EHDS and EOSC, with focus on interoperable cataloguing and the potential adoption of the HealthDCAT-AP metadata standard as a common ground. It is important to recognize that EHDS Data Catalogue is distinct and independent from EU Datasets Catalogue²² and EOSC Resource Hub (although they might be all to some extent interoperable through the underlying use of DCAT-AP, of which HealthDCAT is an extension). In the context of EHDS, the national catalogues (operated by HDABs) have to feed into the EU Datasets Catalogue based on the requirements set by the regulation. In EOSC, non-personal health-related datasets (e.g., extreme weather data, pollutants data, antimicrobial usage data) metadata may be linked to datasets included in the EU Datasets Catalogue. EHDS and EOSC federation should pursue interoperability at the level of services and metadata specifications, exploiting the efforts of EHDS in HealthDCAT-AP, the EOSC Interoperability framework, the EOSC PID infrastructure and the technical specifications of services.
2. **Data access application**²³ ("health data access application"²⁴ and "data permit"²⁵ by HDABs and "access approval"²⁶ by authorised participants in EHDS terms): Navigating the different legal bases for data access and reuse (EHDS regulation providing a new legal basis for reuse without consent versus based on legal obligation, vs. access based on existing legal bases such as

²² <https://data.europa.eu/en>

²³ 'Permit application' in the Figure

²⁴ EHDS, Art. 67

²⁵ EHDS, Art. 68

²⁶ EHDS, Art. 2, §1(u), Art 61 §1 and §3, Art. 68 §8 - authorised participants may provide access approval, but may not issue data permit

informed consent through Research Infrastructures participating in EOSC) and aligning technical systems for user authentication and authorization (e.g., eIDAS and AARC). EOSC AAI in the EOSC EU Node supports EU Login (eIDAS); as a part of building EOSC Federation, community-specific AAI such as LifeScience AAI²⁷ are integrating themselves with EOSC AAI. Therefore, EOSC and EHDS services can be interoperable at the level of the authentication. On the level of authorising access application, the only possible way to make them interoperable, is by EOSC nodes becoming authorised participants and then their decision making can be consulted and coordinated with the decision making of HDABs. Otherwise from the legal perspective, EHDS decisions must be independent from EOSC.

3. **Data preparation and provision:** EOSC services related to knowledge graphs and other services in EOSC provided by Research Infrastructures that link different related research objects will also facilitate the discovery of additional information relevant for conducting the research. The link to cross-discipline data in EOSC will be relevant for research studies that require socioeconomic, environmental mobility or any other relevant data, for example when addressing One Health use cases. In any case, any data preparation and provisioning in EHDS is possible after a data permit is issued.
4. **Data use:** Ensuring secure data analysis by potentially aligning EOSC's Trusted Research Environments (TREs) with EHDS's Secure Processing Environments²⁸ (SPEs), and addressing the need for established well-defined software. On one hand, EOSC software registries and best practices can facilitate SPE software availability, control, software provenance as well as cross domain experience gathered under the EOSC. On the other hand, EHDS actors can leverage specific experience on the management of sensitive data for research, by revising architectures, expanding requirements and reusing existing developments in EOSC. Even if EOSC TREs are technically aligned with EHDS SPEs, the overall compliance with EHDS legal and security requirements remains mandatory for any secondary use of health data and HDABs have the capacity to accept or reject use of a specific TRE as an SPE.
5. **Reusability of Data and Outputs:** Maximizing the value of research by focusing on results retrieved from SPEs, managing data provenance, and leveraging EOSC's expertise in FAIR principles and reproducibility to support EHDS objectives. The results obtained in activities related in the frame of EHDS can be preserved in EOSC research object registries, as long its "check out" from the SPE has been authorised by the corresponding HDAB; hence only non-personal anonymised research results qualify for this. Archiving and reproducibility support as such is within the remit of EHDS (data archiving will be defined as a part of data permit based on user requirements specified in the data access application process). EOSC can describe in detail the standards, formats, policies and services for the registration and reuse of research output and EHDS define the restrictions related to the reusability policies. Such reuse must respect the data permit conditions and cannot involve personal or pseudonymised data.

It is important to note that the previous points are focussed on the instrument of Data Access Application and the processing of data based on legal obligation of Data permit²⁹ issued by a HDAB. Additionally, there is an alternate instrument, the **Health Data Request**³⁰, where data is processed by the HDAB directly and only anonymised statistical results are provided to the data user.

²⁷ <https://lifescience-ri.eu/ls-login.html>

²⁸ EHDS, Art. 73

²⁹ EHDS, Art. 68

³⁰ EHDS, Art. 69

The summary document, linked previously, also includes Figure 4 which proposes several elements to exchange between the two ecosystems. This Figure served as a starting point for the further discussion of the Health Data Task Force.

Figure 4: Illustrative diagram with some possible interactions between EHDS and EOSC discussed at the meeting. Note that a given partner can play different roles. Note that the directionality of arrows is bound to the label.

In summary, the EHDS is a regulatory and infrastructural initiative specifically designed to address the unique challenges of sharing and reusing sensitive health data. It establishes a controlled, secure environment with clear rules and governance for accessing data for specific, permitted purposes. The major change introduced by the regulation is that it obliges health data holders to expose and share the data they hold under such rules. The EOSC, on the other hand, is a bottom-up approach, promoting a cultural shift towards Open Science by federating existing research infrastructures and services to make a broad range of scientific data more discoverable and reusable. While both aim to unlock the value of data, the EHDS takes a more prescriptive, top-down approach for a specific, highly sensitive sector, while the EOSC takes a more federated, community-driven approach to data sharing across all scientific disciplines. Table 1 presents the different features of this comparison.

Note that simultaneous participation in both EHDS and EOSC is likely to incur additional costs for the data holders. While participation in the EHDS is a legal requirement, the participation in EOSC is voluntary. Hence the data holders need to assess the benefits and costs of participating in EOSC. Possible benefits to be considered include: (i) implementation of obligations on open publishing of non-personal data stated in EHDS Art. 60 §5, (ii) implementation of mechanisms not supported by EHDS, such as long-term data transfers based on data transfer agreements, allowing to build large-scale (semi-)permanent integrated data resources. Genuine interoperability between the Data Spaces enables researchers to combine relevant datasets and advance research.

Table 1: Comparison of features covered by the EHDS regulation and its counterpart in EOSC ecosystem

Feature	European Health Data Space (EHDS)	European Open Science Cloud (EOSC)
Scope	Health-specific data space, focusing on electronic health data relevant for human health. ³¹	Multi-disciplinary research data space, for all scientific domains.
Primary Goal	Patient empowerment and secure reuse of electronic health data under defined legal bases and safeguards.	Fostering Open Science and a "Web of FAIR data and services" for researchers.
Data Access Mechanism	Regulated federated access through HDABs via "data permits" ³² and "authorised participants" through "access approvals" ³³ released under their scope. Both HDABs and authorised participants should also implement and support data requests ³⁴ .	Federated system where access for EOSC Federation users is managed by individual data repositories according to FAIR principles.
Data Sensitivity	Highly sensitive personal health data, with a strong emphasis on application of privacy-enhancing technologies (anonymization, pseudonymization) - both when implementing data processing in SPEs ³⁵ and retrieving anonymised statistical results from SPEs or via data requests.	Various levels of data sensitivity, with a focus on making data open where possible, but respecting all relevant legal frameworks (e.g., GDPR). This includes TREs in multiple research domains.
Legal Basis	EHDS regulation introduces a mechanism of "data permit", which is an administrative decision creating "legal obligation" from a GDPR perspective for the involved data holders. Hence it enables access to data which were previously missing a suitable legal basis for being made available for secondary use. Note that the EHDS legal obligation does <i>not</i>	Use of (personal) health data in EOSC has to be based on existing legal basis (most notably informed consent).

³¹ EHDS, Art. 51 §1

³² EHDS, Art. 68

³³ EHDS, Art 2, §1(u), Art 61 §1 and §3, Art. 68 §8. Note that access approvals by authorised participants are *not* administrative decisions in the sense that data permits by HDABs are.

³⁴ EHDS, Art. 69

³⁵ EHDS, Art. 73

Feature	European Health Data Space (EHDS)	European Open Science Cloud (EOSC)
	apply to authorised participants in EHDS and they need to have an existing legal basis: they can only issue “access approval” (which is not an administrative decision and not creating any legal obligation) and not a data permit.	
Infrastructure	New, dedicated digital infrastructure for secondary use (HealthData@EU). However, SPE capacities could be provided by different capacity providers (incl. EOSC providers) as long as they fulfil requirements on SPEs and have been designated or contracted by the competent authors (HDABs, Single Trusted Data Holders). ³⁶	A "system of systems" that federates existing EOSC nodes with national, thematic, and e-infrastructure scope. No legal regulatory framework. Currently a lightweight Memorandum of Understanding is signed by the initial EOSC Nodes. Technical requirements initially relating to identity management and service catalogues and a range of technical recommendations are outlined in the EOSC Federation Handbook.
Architecture	Based on a hub and spoke model with national node implementation by MS and a centralised infrastructure operated by the European Commission.	Based on a model of federation of EOSC nodes, following a MoU among them and the EOSC Association.
Implementation timeline	The Regulation entered into force in March 2025 and applies in stages. For secondary use, key obligations apply from March 2029 (most categories) and March 2031 (remaining categories, incl. genomics). Onboarding of authorised participants from 2029; participation of third countries/international organisations from 2035. ³⁷	EOSC EU Node operational, EOSC Federation commenced in 2025. No legally binding timeframe.
Implementation approach	Country-driven and hierarchical. Implementation and delegated	Mainly bottom-up, with no formal legal and regulatory

³⁶ Based on preliminary results of WP7 of TEHDAS2 project, defining detailed requirements on SPEs.

³⁷ EHDS, Art. 105

Feature	European Health Data Space (EHDS)	European Open Science Cloud (EOSC)
Data User Journey	acts are expected to be designed based on outcomes of the TEHDAS2 project ³⁸ and QUANTUM ³⁹ project for Art.78(6).	framework besides the initial EOSC Handbook requirements and technical recommendations.
	Data discovery. (a) Data access application ⁴⁰ , data permit ⁴¹ , data preparation, data provision, data use & results output. (b) Data request ⁴² .	Similar to restricted data, but different for Open Data (no Permit) and data preparation depends on data sources. It offers research workflows, including data handling, computing, VREs, PIDs and publication of results in open repositories.
Implementation force	Being a regulation, EHDS implementation is compulsory to all the Member States and implementing and delegated acts will define specific components.	Mainly through projects and procurements, contributions required at institutional, national and European level for the time being.
Usage cost model	HDABs should be allowed to charge fees ⁴³ related to their tasks, which can include costs charged by data holders for data preparation and SPE processing costs. Applicants are expected to contribute to these costs, as provided under national arrangements and implementing provisions following the common principles set in the related implementing act.	e-Infrastructure services in EOSC (such as computing and storage) may require quotas or could be based on yet to be developed business models/credit systems.

1.4 On the European Interoperability Framework

The European Interoperability Framework (EIF)⁴⁴ provides the overarching principles, standards, and governance guidelines to ensure that digital systems *across the public administration within the EU* can

³⁸ <https://tehdas.eu/>

³⁹ <https://quantumproject.eu/>

⁴⁰ EHDS, Art. 67

⁴¹ EHDS, Art. 68

⁴² EHDS, Art. 69

⁴³ EHDS, Rec. 70 and Art. 62

⁴⁴ https://ec.europa.eu/isa2/sites/default/files/eif_brochure_final.pdf

work together seamlessly, legally, and securely. Building on this foundation, sector-specific regulations such as the European Health Data Space (EHDS) and policy-driven initiatives such as the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) can put these principles into practice in their respective domains.

The European Interoperability Framework (EIF) is part of the Communication (COM(2017)134)⁴⁵ from the European Commission adopted on 23 March 2017. Its primary goal is to enable the delivery of interoperable and seamless digital public services across borders and sectors, ensuring that public administrations, businesses, and citizens can interact efficiently throughout the European Union.

The idea behind the EIF emerged from the recognition that Europe’s diversity—in languages, legal systems, and administrative cultures—can create barriers to the smooth delivery of digital services. Without a shared understanding of how systems should communicate and operate together, cross-border digital services risk becoming fragmented and inefficient.

The current version, EIF 3.0, published in 2017, reflects the EU’s ambition to build a Digital Single Market, where data and services can flow freely and securely. It sets out a set of principles, models, and recommendations that guide public administrations on how to achieve interoperability. These include principles like openness, transparency, reusability, privacy, and security by design—all crucial for ensuring trust and efficiency in public digital services.

A distinctive feature of the EIF is its conceptual model of interoperability, see Figure 5, which recognizes that true interoperability is not just about technology. It happens at multiple layers:

- At the **legal level**, laws and regulations need to be aligned to allow data sharing. Ensures that public administrations operating under different legal frameworks (e.g., in different EU Member States) can collaborate without legal conflicts.
- At the **organizational level**, business processes must be coordinated. Enables stakeholders to collaboratively agree on how data will be used, managed, and shared in a secure, legal, and coordinated way.
- At the **semantic level**, data must carry the same meaning across systems. Ensures the data is correctly interpreted and meaningful for decision-making.
- And at the **technical level**, IT systems must be able to exchange data reliably. Allows systems to connect and make accessible mobilise data from one point to another, according to the regulatory dispositions

⁴⁵ https://eur-lex.europa.eu/resource.html?uri=cellar:2c2f2554-0faf-11e7-8a35-01aa75ed71a1.0017.02/DOC_1&format=PDF

Figure 5: European Interoperability Framework Model

By following these guidelines, European administrations can make their services more **efficient, interoperable, and future-proof**, reducing administrative burdens on people and businesses, and ensuring that public sector digital transformation is coherent across the EU.

The EIF is closely tied to other EU policies like the **Interoperable Europe Act**⁴⁶ and the **European Data Strategy**⁴⁷. It is worth noting that the EIF served as a major guiding principle in the design work of the EHDS provisions for secondary use, especially in the first TEHDAS Joint Action, but the EHDS remains as an autonomous legal instrument. Additionally, the EIF was also a guiding framework for early EOSC Governance Framework design proposed in the EOSCpilot project.⁴⁸

In general terms, the Health Data Task Force addresses Semantic and Technical interoperability between EOSC and EHDS. Legal and Organisational interoperability within the EHDS is managed by the EHDS regulation itself, which also provides basic framework for the Legal interoperability between EOSC and EHDS (Rec. 80 of EHDS stating that infrastructures federated under EOSC can become authorised participants in EHDS). Hence regarding Organisational and Legal interoperability aspects, the Health Data Task Force can only provide suggestions for EOSC to help align the Organisational interoperability with EHDS. Table 2 contains a summary of how these three levels of interoperability apply to the Health Data Task Force discussions and the current document. Section “(Data) Interoperability and Quality” further develops this conceptual framework.

It is worth noting that the BRIDGE-Health project,⁴⁹ the InfAct Joint action⁵⁰ and the PHIRI⁵¹ were early projects alongside BBMRI-ERIC as a research infrastructure that conceptualised and piloted a European health data sharing ecosystem. The EIF was used to convey the design of a federated research

⁴⁶ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg/2024/903/oj/eng>

⁴⁷ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A52020DC0066>

⁴⁸ EOSCpilot Deliverable 2.6 “Governance Framework for the European Open Science Cloud” <https://eoscipilot.eu/files/sites/default/files/eoscipilot-d2.6-v2.12.pdf>, also available as an on-line report in <https://europeanopensciencecloud.github.io/Governance/>

⁴⁹ <https://www.bridge-health.eu/>, Grant No. 664691

⁵⁰ <https://www.inf-act.eu/>

⁵¹ <https://www.phiri.eu/>

infrastructure for population health research, providing a mapping of the EIF for health data sharing purposes.^{52, 53}

Table 2: Summary of interoperability levels and its application in the Health Data Task Force concepts

Feature	Technical Interoperability	Semantic Interoperability	Organisational Interoperability (for EOSC)
Examples relevant for health data domain (independent of EHDS or EOSC)	Transport protocols, data formats, and connectivity standards (e.g., XML, JSON, eDelivery ⁵⁴ , SIMPL-Open ⁵⁵).	The meaning, context, and coding of data including models, vocabularies, coding system, and ontologies (e.g., FHIR APIs, SNOMED CT, ICD-10, OMOP-CDM).	Policies, governance models, and organizational structures.
In EHDS context	Technical interoperability of the HealthData@EU infrastructure only: Connectors between EU Central Platform and National Contact Points released in the code.europa.eu ⁵⁶ repository. EHDS intentionally does not address any technical interoperability of health data for secondary data.	Secondary use in EHDS (chap. IV): regulation specifies concepts of interoperability for data discovery (HealthDCAT-AP) and quality/utility label. EHDS intentionally does not address any semantic interoperability of health data for secondary data.	Set by the EHDS regulation, followed by related implementing and delegated acts.
In EOSC context	Voluntary, recommended and community-based initiatives. The EOSC Federation Handbook ⁵⁷ makes recommendations on technical interoperability, but requires common federated capabilities in AAI and catalogues. Potential future requirements are outlined in the EOSC Interoperability Framework ^{58,59,60} .	Voluntary community-based initiatives. EOSC Federation Handbook addresses semantic interoperability indirectly, but requires and suggests common federated capabilities (AAI, catalogue required, others optional).	Basic organisational interoperability outlined in EOSC Federation Handbook (currently a lightweight MoU between EOSC Nodes ⁶¹ , not a legal regulatory framework).

⁵² González-García, J., Estupiñán-Romero, F., Tellería-Oriols, C. *et al.* Coping with interoperability in the development of a federated research infrastructure: achievements, challenges and recommendations from the JA-InfAct. *Arch Public Health* 79, 221 (2021). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13690-021-00731-z>

⁵³ González-García J, González-Galindo J, Estupiñán-Romero F, Thißen M, Lyons RA, Telleria-Oriols C, Bernal-Delgado E; Population Health Information Research Infrastructure. PHIRI: lessons for an extensive reuse of sensitive data in federated health research. *Eur J Public Health*. 2024 Jul 1;34(Supplement_1):i43-i49. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1093/eurpub/ckae036>

⁵⁴ <https://ec.europa.eu/digital-building-blocks/sites/spaces/DIGITAL/pages/467110114/eDelivery>

⁵⁵ <https://code.europa.eu/simpl/simpl-open/architecture>

⁵⁶ <https://code.europa.eu/healthdataeu>

⁵⁷ EOSC Association. (2025). EOSC Federation Handbook. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14999577>

⁵⁸ EOSC interoperability framework – Report from the EOSC Executive Board Working Groups FAIR and Architecture, Publications Office, 2021, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/620649>

⁵⁹ Scardaci, D. O., Dimper, R., Wilk, R., Gonzalez Guardia, E., Portier, M., & Van de Sanden, M. (2025). Technical interoperability in the EOSC Federation and initial gap analysis. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17507570>

⁶⁰ Kanellopoulos, C., Adomeit, M., Ardizzzone, V., Florio, L., Giacomini, F., Groep, D., Hardt, M., Kálmán, T., Kuczyński, T., Liampotis, N., Short, H., Sidorova, I., Michal, Š., & Wierenga, K. (2025). EOSC AAI Architecture 2025 (March 2025). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15388270>

⁶¹ https://eosc.eu/wp-content/uploads/2025/10/20251103_MoU_Operational-Preparation_EOSC-Federation.pdf

2 Mapping Existing Landscape

2.1 Analysis of Stakeholders in Data Access and Use

In the European Union today, the stakeholders who access and use health data for research purposes are diverse and operate within a highly regulated framework. This selection of stakeholders is given by the focus of the deliverable; to ensure adequate coverage, the data access and namely data use is understood in a widest sense and covers a broad spectrum of EOSC and EHDS stakeholders, which have relevance to health data. The main types of stakeholders involved may be grouped as follows:

- **Academic research institutions, universities, public and private research centres**, which use data to conduct clinical, epidemiological, biomedical and other studies and are subject to ethics committees and compliance with the GDPR. **Public health bodies**, such as ministries, health agencies, national public health institutes which use data for health surveillance, public health planning and policy evaluation. This category includes all the national health ministries, but also other entities.
- **Hospitals and healthcare systems, healthcare providers**, which collect and share health data in a secure environment participating in clinical research, treatment evaluation registries and biobanks.
- **Private companies and industry, pharmaceutical and biotech companies, digital health start-ups**, which often have access to data via partnerships or secure infrastructures to develop, validate, and test drugs, medical devices and AI solutions in the framework of strict regulatory obligations regarding confidentiality and consent.
- **Private companies producing data generation devices in health(care) and wellness**, whose systems and devices generate data that may later be processed under the EHDS framework or reused via EOSC-compliant research infrastructures, under applicable legal bases. Medical devices: EHR systems. Medical or biological devices: omics, imaging, laboratory devices. Wellness and lifestyle: sports wearables, health monitoring wearables, nutrition and lifestyle monitoring apps.
- **Patient federations and associations**, who are more and more involved in governing or in facilitating access to data, in particular to defend patients' interests. Patients and research participants are also more and more actively acting as data providers, by contributing with data collected with personal informatics devices also using instruments as the data altruism (Data Governance Act Chapter IV⁶²). On the other hand, patients/citizens don't want to be constantly bothered by requests: involvement through dynamic consent or secondary use mechanisms not relying on consent but offering safeguards (i.e. opt-out, transparency) such as the EHDS, is now considered overcome, except for very specific applications.
- **Data infrastructures and platforms, national or regional infrastructures** such as the Health Data Hub (France), NORTRE (Norway), Findata (Finland), or BIGAN (Aragón, Spain) or **Research Infrastructures**, such as BBMRI-ERIC, EuroBioImaging ERIC, ELIXIR, EATRIS-ERIC, which interconnect national data sources through their national nodes, and play an intermediary role, supporting consistent implementation of interoperability, security, regulatory compliance and transparency in data access.

⁶² Regulation (EU) 2022/868 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 30 May 2022 on European data governance and amending Regulation (EU) 2018/1724 (Data Governance Act) (Text with EEA relevance) Art.

- **Standardization bodies** (e.g. ISO, HL7, SNOMED International) whose aim is to ensure that health data is consistent, interoperable, secure, and reusable across systems, countries, and stakeholders.
- **Data protection authorities** (e.g. CNIL in France), which enforce compliance with existing regulations, such as the GDPR, and the protection of individuals' rights when data is processed, complementing the HDABs in their data access authorisation duties.
- **European Union Agencies**, such as the European Medicines Agencies (EMA), the European Center for Diseases Control (ECDC) or the Joint Research Center (JRC), are potential health data users with special consideration in the EHDS regulation. In this group the EMA with its DARWIN Network⁶³ will also be a health data holder heavily experienced in federated data analysis.

These actors currently operate under GDPR and national laws. The EHDS will provide a harmonised EU-level framework for secondary use.

2.2 Sharing and processing health data for research purposes before EHDS

Prior to the adoption of the European Health Data Space (EHDS), the sharing and processing of health data for research purposes in Europe was mainly framed by several rules and legal frameworks. An overview of the situation in different Member States has been provided in 2021 in the EC publication "Assessment of the EU Member States' rules on health data in the light of GDPR"⁶⁴. Furthermore, in 2022, the EOSC-Life project offered a detailed overview of how national health databases and registries are used for secondary research purposes across multiple Member States⁶⁵. Requirements for data sharing and reuse include:

- The General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)⁶⁶: This European regulation, which has been applicable since May 2018, provides a regulatory framework for the collection, processing and sharing of personal data, including health data, which is considered sensitive data. Notably, it establishes general principles and obligations applicable across sectors. Note that most of the health data falls into a special category of data defined by Art. 9 of GDPR, which only permits processing of data under specific conditions⁶⁷. In research, it is essential to handle personal data responsibly and in accordance with data protection legislation. This includes ensuring a valid legal basis for data processing under the GDPR, providing adequate information to participants, and maintaining confidentiality and security throughout the data processing lifecycle. While informed consent is often used, it is not the only – and in many cases not the most appropriate – basis. The GDPR also recognises research carried out in the public interest (Art. 6(1)(e) and Art. 9(2)(j)), processing necessary for reasons of public health (Art. 9(2)(i)), or processing under a legal obligation or the exercise of official authority (Art. 6(1)(c) and (e)) as possible grounds.
- National rules: Complementing the GDPR and EHDS, each EU Member State has its own specific regulations, interpretations, and procedural requirements regarding the use of health data for research purposes. These differences included varying approaches to ethical approval, data

⁶³ <https://www.ema.europa.eu/en/about-us/how-we-work/data-regulation-big-data-other-sources/real-world-evidence/data-analysis-real-world-interrogation-network-darwin-eu>

⁶⁴ https://health.ec.europa.eu/publications/assessment-eu-member-states-rules-health-data-light-gdpr_en

⁶⁵ <https://zenodo.org/records/7148861>

⁶⁶ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:02016R0679-20160504>

⁶⁷ GDPR, Art. 9, §2.

access permissions, and legal bases for processing, often resulting in fragmented practices and legal uncertainty. As a consequence, researchers faced significant administrative and legal barriers when attempting to conduct cross-border studies, limiting the scalability and efficiency of European health research.

- Ethical frameworks and ethics committees: Research involving health data often requires review by ethics committees to ensure the protection of patients' rights. Note that EHDS and national ethics committees' regulations are independent and EHDS does neither harmonize nor affect ethical review procedures. While the legal basis for processing health data for research under the GDPR does not always require explicit consent, participants are often asked to provide informed consent when involved in research studies, particularly in clinical or interventional settings. Under the GDPR, alternative legal bases such as processing necessary for scientific research in the public interest⁶⁸ may often provide a more sustainable framework
- Specific research programmes and infrastructures: Prior to enforcement of the EHDS regulation, a number of EU-wide infrastructures and initiatives were set with the aim of fostering the harmonisation and secure sharing of data, but implemented in limited and fragmented domains such as the BBMRI Federated Platform⁶⁹ and BBMRI cohorts^{70,71}, the EBRAINS Medical Informatics Platform⁷², and complemented by various project and initiatives leading to implementation including Population Health Information Research Infrastructure (PHIRI)⁷³, the European Health Data Evidence Network (EHDEN)⁷⁴, the European Cancer Image Initiative (EUCAIM)⁷⁵ or the Genomics Data Initiative (GDI)⁷⁶.

Within this complex ecosystem, the EHDS Regulation now provides a common, directly applicable EU framework for the secondary use of electronic health data. EHDS (as a complementary non-exclusive mechanism) introduces a legal basis for such processing under Union law, complements the GDPR, and harmonises procedures for data discovery, access, and use through HealthData@EU. By introducing shared governance structures, metadata and cataloguing standards, and secure processing environments (SPEs), it enables high-quality, data protection compliant research without the need to transfer personal data outside secure environments.

The EHDS regulation is expected to help with reducing the current reliance on consent for making data accessible for secondary use. It is important to stress, however, that EHDS is not a legal basis for data holders to collect data - i.e., data collected for research purposes will still need to be based on informed consent or other suitable legal basis by the data holder.

⁶⁸ GDPR, Art. 6 §1(e) and Art. 9 §2(j)

⁶⁹ <https://www.bbmri-eric.eu/news-events/bbmri-eric-launches-the-federated-platform/>

⁷⁰ <https://www.healthinformationportal.eu/research-network/bbmri-large-prospective-cohorts>

⁷¹ <https://www.bbmri-eric.eu/scientific-collaboration/colorectal-cancer-cohort/>

⁷² <https://mip.ebrains.eu/>

⁷³ <https://www.phiri.eu/>

⁷⁴ <https://www.ehden.eu/>

⁷⁵ <https://cancerimage.eu/>

⁷⁶ <https://gdi.onemilliongenomes.eu/>

2.2.1 On Data Transfer Agreements

The sensitivity of health-related information renders its processing and dissemination particularly challenging from a legal and ethical perspective. The GDPR designates health data as a *special category of personal data*⁷⁷, thereby subjecting its use to heightened safeguards and, in principle, a prohibition of processing unless specific conditions apply. This dual imperative—to facilitate data-driven scientific progress while upholding fundamental rights to privacy and data protection—has intensified the search for robust governance mechanisms capable of reconciling these objectives.

Within this regulatory landscape, **Data Transfer Agreements (DTAs)** have gained prominence as contractual instruments that operationalize GDPR principles in concrete data sharing arrangements. DTAs define data transfers between data controllers, including requirements on technical and organizational safeguards to be implemented and any limitations of the intended uses. They also serve to standardize practices across jurisdictions and institutions, thus reducing legal uncertainty and fostering trust among stakeholders. Importantly, DTAs act as a bridge between the abstract requirements of the GDPR and the practical realities of collaborative research, providing a framework through which compliance, accountability, and ethical integrity can be demonstrated.

Projects, such as HealthyCloud,⁷⁸ explored how to facilitate the creation of DTAs. For example, Deliverable 2.2 “*Framework of modular contract clauses for HRICs*”⁷⁹ provided a framework of well-defined DTA contractual clauses that can be reused in a modular manner.

Under the EHDS regulation, the legal basis complemented by organisational and technical measures including mandatory use of Secure Processing Environments (SPEs) and the authorisation system based on data permits remove the need for Data Transfer Agreements between holders and users. The legal disclosure obligation of data holders under the Regulation replaces the contractual transfer framework. DTAs remain relevant only for transfers or cooperation taking place outside the EHDS scope, including international contexts.

2.2.2 Clinical trial and cohort data

Sharing and reusing clinical trial data and data from observational cohort studies raises additional technical, legal, ethical and cultural challenges. This is why implementation remains low, despite increasing pressure from key stakeholders in clinical research such as medical journal editors⁸⁰, funders⁸¹ and industry⁸² to accelerate the adoption of the FAIR principles in the field. In clinical trials, the intention to share study data for future research is documented early through the data sharing statement required at the time of study registration (e.g., on [ClinicalTrials.gov](https://clinicaltrials.gov), CTIS⁸³). Literature reports estimate that the percentage of clinical trials willing to share data with external researchers does not exceed 15%⁸⁴. To

⁷⁷ GDPR, Art. 9

⁷⁸ <https://healthycloud.eu/>

⁷⁹ Adrian Thorogood. (2022). Framework of modular contract clauses for HRICs. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10260164>

⁸⁰ Taichman DB, Backus J, Baethge C. et al. Sharing Clinical Trial Data: A Proposal from the International Committee of Medical Journal Editors. PLoS Med. 2016;13(1):e1001950. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pmed.1001950>.

⁸¹ Coetzee T, Ball MP, Boutin M. et al. Data Sharing Goals for Nonprofit Funders of Clinical Trials. J Particip Med. 2021;13(1):e23011. <https://doi.org/10.2196/23011>.

⁸² <https://www.efpia.eu/media/qndlfduy/phrmaefpiaprinciplesforresponsibledatasharing2023.pdf>

⁸³ <https://euclinicaltrials.eu/>

⁸⁴ Larson K, Sim I, von Isenburg M, et al. COVID-19 interventional trials: analysis of data sharing intentions during a time of pandemic. Contemporary Clinical Trials. 2022;115:106709

enable clinical trial data sharing in the European Economic Area (EEA), it is often necessary to prepare a dedicated Participant Information Sheet and obtain informed consent that clearly outlines the potential for data sharing and secondary use in as much detail as possible. Repositories for long term clinical trial data storage and sharing exist (e.g., Vivli⁸⁵, ClinicalStudyDataRequest⁸⁶, IDDO⁸⁷, ECRIN crDSR⁸⁸). These repositories have rigorous data governance and data access and reuse processes but they are currently not widely used. For now, the most common way to share (pseudonymised or anonymised) clinical trial data is through direct email to the study sponsor or principal investigator (PI), who, after reviewing the proposed secondary use project and having normally requested ethics approval, initiates a secure file transfer following the signing of a contractual agreement.

Unlike clinical trials, which are governed by harmonised procedures under the EU Clinical Trials Regulation (Regulation (EU) No 536/2014), observational cohort studies lack such uniformity and are characterised by considerable heterogeneity. As the registration of cohort studies is not mandated, their findability is limited and typically depends on screening publication databases (e.g., PubMed). Harmonisation of variables across prospective cohorts to enable their integration is a major challenge in the field - a challenge unaffected by EHDS. For data access and reuse, each cohort sets their own rules, in line with the applicable legislation and institutional policies but the process often includes: i) a secondary use application, ii) scientific evaluation of the secondary use proposal, iii) ethics approval, iv) data sent via secure file transfer after signature of contractual agreements. It is common that the original research team gets involved in the secondary use project and requires review of any results of the secondary use project before publication. While informed consent obtained at recruitment is frequently used as the legal basis for sharing prospective cohort data, it is not always considered sufficiently robust for secondary use.

Other legal and governance mechanisms may provide a more stable foundation, particularly for large-scale or long-term research projects. The upcoming EHDS regulation clarifies and harmonises these approaches across Member States, thereby reducing the current over reliance on consent through an opt-out mechanism for retrospective cohorts and contributing to more consistent governance of cohort data. In parallel, the EHDS' emphasis on common standards for metadata, cataloguing, and semantic interoperability may also help overcome the heterogeneity of cohort variables, supporting more seamless integration and cross-cohort research.

Note that EHDS does address this field, since data from clinical trials (after the trial has ended) and data from research cohorts are explicitly noted as data categories which are in scope for secondary use.⁸⁹ This means that data holders still need a suitable legal basis for primary collection of the data (note EHDS is not a basis for data holders collecting data!), the EHDS legal obligation can be used as a legal basis for secondary use instead of consent or any other legal basis, and the data can also be made accessible via the respective HDAB.

In summary, the EHDS complements a patchwork of national and project-based arrangements with a single Union-level framework that defines lawful access, eliminates most cross-border transfer obstacles, and embeds data protection safeguards directly into its technical architecture.

⁸⁵ <https://vivli.org/>

⁸⁶ <https://www.clinicalstudydatarequest.com/>

⁸⁷ <https://www.iddo.org/>

⁸⁸ <https://crdsr.ecrin.org/login>

⁸⁹ EHDS, Art 51 §1(m) and §1(p) respectively, and Rec. 56

2.3 Sharing and processing health data for secondary purposes in EHDS

Under the European Health Data Space (EHDS), the sharing and processing of health data for secondary purposes (i.e. uses other than direct healthcare, such as research, public policy development, innovation, or health service planning) are organised with several key safeguards and rules:

- Facilitating access and re-use: The EHDS will facilitate secure access to health data for secondary purposes, creating an environment where data can be shared more easily between Member States, while complying with current legislation.
- Strict respect for privacy and individual rights: Access to data will be subject to compliance with the GDPR and the principles of data minimization, anonymization or pseudonymization where possible, in order to protect the privacy of data subjects. Even data access in EHDS will not require the explicit patient consent, the EHDS introduces an opt-out mechanism where individuals can withdraw their data for secondary use
- Governance mechanisms: The EHDS sets up specific infrastructures, such as national contact points, health data access bodies to supervise and regulate requests for access to data for secondary purposes.
- Coexistence with other legal bases: The EHDS regulation applies without prejudice to other legal frameworks (GDPR, Clinical Trials Regulation, Data Governance Act, etc.), and that reuse outside EHDS must rely on an independent legal basis.
- Transparency and traceability are ensured through public information portals and the register of data permits managed by HDABs. Each data user must provide a summary of the results of the data processing, which are made publicly available.
- Encouraging research and innovation: By simplifying access and ensuring robust governance, the EHDS aims to stimulate health research and the development of new technologies, treatments and services, while ensuring high standards of security and ethics.

In consequence under the EHDS, the sharing and processing of health data for secondary purposes will be regulated to ensure a balance between the exploitation of secondary data for uses which benefit society and the protection of individuals' rights and privacy.

3 Data Hosting, Discoverability and Accessibility

3.1 Existing landscape

The European Health Data Space (EHDS) and the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) are intended to be pivotal to the secondary use and sharing of data in Europe for research. EHDS is a sector-specific initiative that targets health data, with a legal and governance framework for secondary use. EOSC on the other hand is a cross-disciplinary ecosystem providing infrastructure for open science.

The reuse of health data—known as "secondary use"—is a critical area where data fragmentation in Europe has a significant impact. This refers to the use of data for purposes beyond direct patient care, such as for research, public health, policymaking, and innovation.

The current situation is one of systemic barriers that hinder scientific progress. Historically, this has been an issue due to a patchwork of national interpretations of the GDPR and a lack of interoperable standards. There is an implicit challenge regarding secondary use of health data, and it is that, due to its nature, those institutions that host the data for their primary purposes in general have little incentives to curate such data for secondary purposes. Some exceptions are those academic hospitals, heavily involved in research

and innovation activities and other research infrastructures. The EHDS will address this by introducing clear obligations for data holders to make certain categories of electronic health data available for secondary use.

Researchers commonly struggle to identify sources of data of interest for their purposes and then, to get access to data hosted in different hospitals or registries because of varying data formats and governance rules. This forces researchers to spend vast amounts of time and resources on administrative processes and additional stages of data preparation, and cleaning, in order to carry out scientific research.

Clearly there is a need to adopt solutions that permit data discoverability and interoperability, while adhering to FAIR principles, one of the fundamental pillars of the EOSC construction. Both EHDS and EOSC face challenges in harmonising metadata standards, catalogues, and interoperability protocols, but there is also a clear potential for synergy, especially in aligning technical interoperability developments and facilitating the exchange of data between infrastructures.⁹⁰ Both EHDS and EOSC aim to improve data discoverability and interoperability through common metadata standards. While EOSC promotes cross-disciplinary FAIR principles, EHDS exclusively focuses on health and health-related data. EHDS also does not handle interoperability of data for secondary use - only interoperability of metadata for catalogue-based discovery.

3.2 Gap Analysis, redundancies and opportunities

In terms of the data hosting, it is possible to identify a major gap in both initiatives. At this point, the EOSC Federation is not providing specific hosting services for health data, or sensitive data in general, even though it is expected that EOSC Nodes may in future provide such services. In the case of the EHDS, the regulation only covers the data storage requirements when processing data to proceed to its provision in an SPE⁹¹ The regulation obliges that data storage and preparation and exposure of metadata is covered by data holders, but data holders are not expected to create new hosting services.

When it comes to data discoverability and accessibility, the EHDS regulation establishes clear governance rules— though even here there is some room for national implementations for data access permit decisions— and interoperability solutions (see next section), most of which are still under development. In this subject, the joint action Towards the European Health Data Space (TEHDAS), finished on July 31, 2023, led to recommendations on what the EHDS could look like. In the continuity TEHDAS2 (Towards a European Health Data Space 2) project input is being prepared for the implementing acts and guidance materials for EHDS implementation. Note that TEHDAS, TEHDAS2 and EHDS2Pilot deliverables are non-binding preparatory work. These projects inform the Commission’s ongoing preparatory work for implementing acts and guidance but do not themselves establish any binding rules.

The landscape of projects related to TEHDAS and EHDS is particularly rich, combining an initial conceptual framework (TEHDAS), technical implementation (TEHDAS2, EHDS2 Pilot, SHAIPE⁹²), and structural support (Capacity Building, Direct Grants to Member States, QUANTUM). These projects support national authorities and the Commission in implementing the EHDS architecture under the EU4Health, Horizon Europe and Digital Europe Programmes.

⁹⁰ <https://tehdas.eu/app/uploads/2023/10/tehdas-recommendations-to-enhance-interoperability.pdf>

⁹¹ EHDSR, Art. 87

⁹² <https://shaiped.eu/>

- EHDS2 Pilot⁹³ (October 2022–December 2024): led by the French Health Data Hub, this project tested technical solutions and promoted interoperability, as well as the implementation modalities of the EHDS2 infrastructure.
- Capacity Building (ongoing project): a DG SANTE led procurement, the project is focused on producing training material (use of HDABs, national catalogues, access request management systems, TRE/SPE, data quality) disseminated via the EU Academy platform.
- Community of Practice (CoP HDABs - ongoing voluntary gathering of MS competent authorities): community of practice aimed at promoting the exchange of best practices between competent authorities for the reuse of health data within the EHDS.
- QUANTUM:⁹⁴ European project (35 partners - ongoing project) aimed at developing a labelling system to assess and communicate the quality of datasets for scientific and health purposes
- SHAIPEd:⁹⁵ led by the French Health Data Hub, this project aims at advancing the European Health Data Space as a facilitator of the artificial intelligence (AI) Act implementation, driving innovation in AI medical devices.

In all cases, EHDS-building projects' deliverables are non-binding preparatory work. These projects inform the Commission's ongoing preparatory work for implementing acts and guidance but, again, do not themselves establish any binding rules.

In the case of EOOSC, the data discoverability and accessibility described [earlier in the document](#), defines Federating Capabilities for EOOSC Nodes that will facilitate data discoverability through Resource Catalogue and Registry services.

3.3 Identified synergies & opportunities

We identify the primary synergy as the potential for technical and policy alignment between EOOSC and the EHDS based on the following:

- EHDS health data holders can leverage the infrastructure of EOOSC for data hosting, considering the health data particularities. EHDS may technically benefit from EOOSC's experience in providing secure data environments, as documented in EOOSC ENTRUST, where such providers fully comply with EHDS Secure Processing Environment (SPE) requirements and governance rules.
- EOOSC can enhance discovery of non-sensitive metadata or facilitate privacy-preserving federated queries, provided such functionalities respect the EHDS framework and do not involve direct access to personal data.
- EOOSC can benefit from the legal and governance clarity provided by EHDS for sensitive health data, using EHDS mechanisms as a model for responsible data sharing and access control.
- EOOSC Order Management services could serve as a technical inspiration for developing interoperable access-request interfaces within national EHDS implementations, without affecting EHDS governance.
- EOOSC can further harmonize and cultivate data access mechanisms based on Data Transfer Agreements, which is out of scope of EHDS –for use cases where EHDS-based user journeys for

⁹³ <https://ehds2pilot.eu/>

⁹⁴ <https://quantumproject.eu/>

⁹⁵ <https://shaiped.eu/>

data requests or data permits (and hence use of SPEs) is not suitable (e.g., building of large centralised repositories of specialised international patient cohorts).

- EOSC can develop common templates for Data Transfer Agreements and Data Processing Agreements applicable to processing of sensitive research data outside the EHDS framework or in the preparatory stages preceding SPE-based analysis.
- There is potential to align metadata standards (e.g., HealthDCAT-AP) across EHDS and EOSC to improve discoverability and reduce duplication, while keeping EHDS dataset catalogues legally and operationally distinct.

4 (Data) Interoperability and Quality

4.1 Existing landscape

Health data interoperability, encompassing both technical and semantic dimensions, represents a complex and multifaceted challenge. Its evolution is profoundly shaped by the concerted efforts of numerous international and national harmonization initiatives, which together form an intricate mosaic of standards and specifications.

4.1.1 Interoperability and quality in the EHDS

Following the EIF framework, the EHDS regulation tackles all interoperability levels when it comes to the interoperability of the EHDS as an infrastructure; yet, as it is explained below, it intentionally does not prescribe how technical and semantic interoperability of the health data and data sets is addressed. *Legal interoperability* is implemented by the EHDS regulation itself, and will be complemented by Implementing and delegated acts that follow from the regulation⁹⁶.

At the *organisational level*, the regulation defines a series of actors, the most representative of which are the following:

1. the Member States must establish a Health Data Access Body (HDAB) responsible for granting permits to use data and ensuring that datasets can be discovered through a national catalogue and data is accessed in a standardised manner through a secure processing environment;
2. Health Data Holders—in general, those companies, public or private, that are data controllers for health data⁹⁷—, will be obliged to expose such datasets by cataloguing them and sharing such information with HDABs;
3. Health Data Users, the end clients of such a data space, representing those individuals interested in accessing health data to perform their day-to-day activities—i.e., research, policy making, regulation or innovation—;
4. an EU Central Platform, operated by the European Commission, which will provide a centralised EU catalogue of datasets (Art.79) and will serve as an entry point to coordinate the data access requests;

⁹⁶ See https://health.ec.europa.eu/document/download/4dd47ec2-71dd-49fc-b036-ad7c14f6ed68_en?filename=ehealth_ehds_qa_de.pdf page 8. The following implementing acts are expected: Art. 13(4) on data quality requirements in primary use; Art. 15(1) on the technical specifications for the EEHRxF; Art. 23(4) on MyHealth@EU; Art. 36(1) on common specifications for the harmonised components of EHR systems; Art. 70(1) on templates for data access applications, permits, and requests; Art. 73(5) on requirements for secure processing environments; Art. 75(12) on HealthData@EU; Art. 77(4) on the requirements for dataset descriptions; Art. 78(6) on the data quality and utility label.

⁹⁷ EHDS, Art.2 §2(t), with the exception of independent researchers and for micro-enterprises, Art.50(1).

5. Research and Data Infrastructures can contribute to the EHDS in form of Authorised Participants.

As stated in the previous section, the regulation leaves some room for Member State level governance rules in the decision-making process on granting the permits, but it is in the spirit of the law to reach some level of mutual coordination between MS decisions, when a health data user requests similar data sets from multiple health data access bodies⁹⁸.

At the *semantic level*, also mentioned in the previous section, the EHDS regulation is focusing on defining a common format for data access requests and, very importantly, the way the metadata about datasets are exposed and catalogued, through defining an extension for the DCAT-AP metadata format named HealthDCAT-AP. This will be key to ensure data discoverability ensuring that data, wherever it originates, can be findable.

In terms of the *technical interoperability*, the EHDS also foresees the creation of HealthData@EU: a secure cross-border infrastructure that follows a hub and spoke model around the EU central platform connecting all national contact points to secondary use and to facilitate HDABs in the exchange of data access applications and data requests and data permits. The Commission will run a central platform⁹⁹, which will act as an information exchange hub with supporting services—exposing the EU datasets catalogue, exchanging information on requests, ensuring security, and possibly offering a common secure processing environment for data analysis when cross-border projects require it.¹⁰⁰ Initial prototypes for the software connectors between HDABs and the central platform and access management system were developed as part the EHDS2Pilot project¹⁰¹ and production implementation is currently underway by EC Central Services, with regular updates presented to the EHDS Community of Practice. Last, but not least, another core technical component of the HealthData@EU infrastructure which enforces significant interoperability requirements are the SPEs. High-level requirements on SPEs are stated in the EHDS regulation¹⁰², while more detailed implementation requirements are to be regulated under the EHDS implementing acts, for which input materials are being discussed in the TEHDAS2 Joint Action¹⁰³.

The EHDS Regulation deliberately refrains from prescribing dataset formats for secondary use. This flexibility avoids excessive implementation burdens and allows specialised communities to maintain and evolve domain-specific semantic and syntactic standards aligned with the EHDS framework. This is therefore a possible role for specific communities in health-related data spaces: to support implementation of the EHDS by reaching and updating a consensus on semantic and syntactic interoperability within their remit. Examples of these include BBMRI, ECRIN, EUCAIM, GDI, and, possibly, contributors of the EOSC Federation.

Regarding the *data quality*, the EHDS regulation defines¹⁰⁴ the creation of data quality and utility labels that may accompany health datasets made available through the EHDS. Data quality labels will be applied

⁹⁸ EHDS, Art. 55 §1 and Art 57 §1(i) - however, based on Art. 68 §5, HDABs and authorised participants are supposed to inform each other about their decisions and may take them into consideration, but they are not obliged to follow any coordinated approach.

⁹⁹ EHDS, Art.75 §8

¹⁰⁰ EHDS, Rec. 80, Art.75 §9

¹⁰¹ <https://code.europa.eu/healthdataeu-nodes>

¹⁰² EHDS, Art. 73

¹⁰³ As of writing this deliverable (09/2025), public consultation has started on TEHDAS2 M7.4 Draft technical, functional and security specifications of Secure Processing Environments.

¹⁰⁴ EHDS Art. 78

to health data holders that maximise the potential for secondary use of their data, encouraging also the increase of data quality by pursuing highest value labels. The actual definition of the label has been proposed¹⁰⁵ as the main outcome of the QUANTUM project, built in a consensus effort through a large number stakeholders. The current proposal, that aims to evaluate dataset quality and fitness-for-use,¹⁰⁶ and includes elements regarding data holders' maturity. It is developed by quantifying and ranking the 22 specific datasets characteristics and processes, grouped into the 6 categories of data quality dimensions defined in the EHDS regulation¹⁰⁷. This is a major effort towards the standardisation of the evaluation of quality and utility.

4.1.2 Interoperability and quality in the EOSC

The EOSC Federation has developed a vision to become an interconnected and interoperable system-of-systems building on European research data infrastructures.

In terms of legal interoperability, the EOSC is not supported by any EU regulatory framework, and its development relies on a voluntary basis and the common approaches of the research agendas of the different Member States and associated countries. The current governance model aims to facilitate that by representatives of the research ministries of the different countries working together in the EOSC Steering Board which forms a Tripartite Governance for EOSC along with the EC and EOSC Association.

A major focus of EOSC initiatives over the last decade has been to tackle a range of interoperability challenges and most recently through the formation of the EOSC Federation¹⁰⁸. The EOSC Federation Handbook builds on work in agreeing e.g. common access and identity management (AAI) standards and services as well as common catalogue requirements. The Federation comprises a number of internal Working Groups building on previous efforts to improve the EOSC interoperability including the semantic interoperability and other related activities. The EOSC Federation itself launched in November 2025 with an initial set of national and thematic Nodes following the signing of the Memorandum of Understanding, and has been supported by a range of new and ongoing INFRA-EOSC projects, including EOSC United and EOSC Gravity.

Organisational interoperability has been embodied in the EOSC Nodes, the main actors of the Federation, whose interconnection will be the foundation of the EOSC concept. There will be a certain number of requirements for such EOSC nodes, especially regarding their sustainability and their capacity to implement core capabilities (see Introduction). Some of these core capabilities are tackled at other levels of interoperability (e.g., the technical solutions).

Recommendations for semantic interoperability in EOSC are described in Chapter 5 of the Federation Handbook, and cover the standards the community propose for research resources to be shared across the EOSC Federation, including: research publications, research data sources, research data, research software, research services and research training. The reusability of research data and outputs is being addressed through the promotion of Persistent Identifiers (PIDs) and rich metadata. Communities are

¹⁰⁵Daumas, J., Schäfer, A., Dolanski-Aghamanoukjan, L., Weishäupl, K., Kuhrn, M. M., Schutte, N., Proietti Mercuri, C., & Bernal-Delgado, E. (2025). *Deliverable 1.1 Specification of the data sets' quality and utility label (2.3.0)*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14937423>

¹⁰⁶ TODO: add reference, differentiating from fitness for purpose

¹⁰⁷ EHDS, Art.78 §3

¹⁰⁸ <https://eosc.eu/building-the-eosc-federation>

building on solutions like RO-Crate¹⁰⁹ which is a structured package for sharing research data and standards like ISO 23494 are being leveraged to ensure that research objects are well-described and citable. The document also references distributed provenance chains, using standards like ISO 23494-2, to track the origin and history of data.

Derived from the EOSC Node core capabilities, the EOSC Federation Handbook provides various technical interoperability elements: **AAI**, built on the AARC framework will also support eIDAS (the same source of government-backed identities for authentication expected to be used by the EHDS to support authentication); recommendations for Service monitoring; Order Management; Configuration Management System; Application Workflow Management; and Resource Provisioning. As covered in the Handbook, the EOSC EU Node is providing Federating Capabilities for such services that might serve as reference implementations for any Node in the Federation.

The EOSC Federation Handbook also references the quality of the service provision—assumed as the availability and response times—; quality assurance for training developed, referencing the Skills4EOSC project guidelines; and, the use of PIDs and metadata standards as described in FAIR-IMPACT guidelines. The Federation Handbook also claims that the EOSC Federation “*will promote the development and adoption of common standards and best practices to improve data quality*”. In a report¹¹⁰ developed by the EOSC Association FAIR Metrics and Data Quality Task Force, a comprehensive approach was presented on how to tackle data quality in the EOSC ecosystem, which is expected to serve as the conceptual framework for future revisions of the Federation Handbook.

Table 3: Comparison on levels of interoperability in EHDS regulation and in the EOSC Federation.

Levels of interoperability	EHDS regulation	EOSC Federation
Legal	EHDS regulation	No binding legal framework / voluntary coordination
Organisational	EU central platform, Health Data Access Bodies, Health Data Holders Health Data Users, Authorised Participants, Single Trusted Data Holders	EOSC Tripartite, EOSC Nodes
Semantic	HealthDCAT-AP (data cataloguing), Common Data Access Forms (data access)	Research Resources: research publications, research data sources, research data, research software, research services and research training
Technical	HealthData@EU infrastructure: EU connectors / MSS connectors (general connectivity), SPE implementing acts (data processing)	EOSC Federation EOSC EU Node blueprint and interoperability

¹⁰⁹ <https://www.researchobject.org/ro-crate/>

¹¹⁰ Lacagnina, C., David, R., Nikiforova, A., Kuusniemi, M. E., Cappiello, C., Biehlaier, O., Wright, L., Schubert, C., Bertino, A., Thiemann, H., & Dennis, R. (2023). *TOWARDS A DATA QUALITY FRAMEWORK FOR EOSC (1.0.0)*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7515816>

While EOSC pursues voluntary alignment of standards and best practices across scientific disciplines, the EOSC Federation mandates requirements on Nodes for identity management and service catalogues, the EHDS Regulation establishes binding requirements for interoperability, governance, and data quality in the health domain. Interoperability between the two frameworks should therefore focus on metadata standards and technical compatibility, without merging their legal or operational responsibilities.

4.1.3 International and National Standardisation Bodies and Collaborative Development Organisations

A foundational layer of overarching interoperability approaches is established by accredited international standardization organisations. The **International Organisation for Standardisation (ISO)**, through its various technical committees, plays a pivotal role. **ISO Technical Committee 215** addresses medical informatics, while **TC 276** focuses on biotechnology. **TC 212** is dedicated to medical laboratories and in vitro diagnostics, and **ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 29/WG 9** has developed various data compression formats including **MPEG-G** standard for genomic data. These committees collectively provide the core technical specifications that underpin data exchange. Europe-centred standardisation efforts are then pursued by **CEN/CENELEC**¹¹¹, the European Committee for Standardisation, which brings together national standardisation bodies of 34 European countries. CEN uses similar structure of technical committees¹¹² as ISO and CEN standards can be taken up by the respective committees of ISO for international standardisation.

Concurrently, **Health Level Seven International (HL7)** has been instrumental in defining the language of health data. While legacy standards such as **HL7 v2** and **v3** remain in use, the current focus is on modern specifications like **HL7 FHIR** and **HL7 CQL**, which are designed for contemporary health information systems. Furthermore, the **National Electrical Manufacturers Association (NEMA)** has provided the long-standing **DICOM** standard, which is essential for the interoperability of medical imaging data.

Beyond these formal bodies, a diverse array of collaborative organisations has emerged to develop and refine community-driven specifications. **SNOMED International (also known as International Health Terminology Standards Development Organisation, IHTSDO)** with 51 member countries and territories manages development of SNOMED CT clinical terminology widely used in electronic health records in health care. The **Observational Health Data Sciences and Informatics (OHDSI)** community has developed the **OMOP Common Data Model**, which standardises the structure of observational health data to facilitate large-scale analytics. **OpenEHR standard** for data modeling of patient-centric electronic health records is maintained by **openEHR Foundation**. Similarly, the **Global Alliance for Genomics and Health (GA4GH)** has created specifications such as **Beacons**, **Passports**, and **DUO** to enable the secure and ethical sharing of genomic and clinical data.

Other notable initiatives include **BBMRI-ERIC**, which has developed **MIABIS** for biobank data and **DUC/CCE** for sample and data access, and the **EUCAIM** project, which is focused on creating specific data models for imaging data.

All in all, the EHDS Regulation does not prescribe specific technical or semantic standards for secondary use. However, the work of these organisations and projects provides essential reference points for

¹¹¹ <https://www.cencenelec.eu/>

¹¹² <https://standards.cencenelec.eu/dyn/www/f?p=CEN:6>

interoperability specifications to be considered in future implementing acts and for voluntary alignment by data holders and service providers.

4.2 Gap Analysis and redundancies

EHDS regulation has intentionally not addressed the standards of choice when it comes to the semantic and technical interoperability of the datasets. Given the amount of standardisation efforts related to health data described above, the domain does not suffer from lack of standardisation, but rather by competition of different standards and lack of practical adoption at data sources. In this context, there are a number of project activities dealing with specific modalities (e.g., BBMRI for biobanking, GDI for genomes or EUCAIM for cancer images), which require integration with broader modalities, in general, including clinical data for its contextualisation. By the nature of the complexity of such large projects, these activities are not always well coordinated or aligned. This leads to the situation that cross-area and cross-discipline semantic interoperability is still an open issue, e.g. One Health, which integrates human, animal and environmental health interactions and data. It's worth noting that breaking these silos will facilitate large scale projects, as recently reported by the EC in: *"The impact of the European Health Data Space Regulation and the Open Data Directive on citizens"*¹¹³. An example from the report is a French project: *Green Data for Health*¹¹⁴ whose aim is to understand how noise (environmental open data) affects sleep (health data) for approximately 10 million French residents.

Technical connectivity solutions for HealthData@EU are being finalised through coordination between the TEHDAS2 Joint Action (recommendations), the European Commission's central services (implementation of the EU platform and connectors), and Member State deployments. Technical interoperability in the EOSC Federation is still under analysis and development, and will remain voluntary and non-binding.

4.3 Identified synergies & opportunities

- Adoption of standards:** both ecosystems will benefit from promoting voluntary adoption of shared standards and frameworks as recommended by the first TEHDAS JA (e.g., DCAT-AP for metadata, and various data standards as HL7-FHIR, or OMOP CDM). EHDS regulation only prescribes the metadata standard (HealthDCAT-AP). EOSC community expertise on fostering the adoption of standards for data FAIRness might define a space to facilitate the education and training required for the Health Data Holders; the risk is, however, limited involvement and authority of EOSC in the health sector, which is the primary data source.
- Harmonise technical interoperability:** For areas where EU-level consensus exists—such as authentication (eIDAS, AARC¹¹⁵) and metadata schemas (DCAT-AP / HealthDCAT-AP)—the EHDS and EOSC Federation implementations should ensure technical compatibility while respecting the EHDS governance and security requirements. In particular, ELIXIR¹¹⁶, BBMRI-ERIC¹¹⁷ and Instruct-ERIC¹¹⁸ teamed up in the EOSC Life project¹¹⁹ to implement an AARC compliant Life

¹¹³ Publications Office of the European Union, Grijnsbach, M., Zwaag, J. v. d. and Page, M., *The impact of the European Health Data Space Regulation and the Open Data Directive on citizens*, Publications Office of the European Union, 2025, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2830/2423642>

¹¹⁴ <https://qd4h.ecologie.gouv.fr/en>

¹¹⁵ <https://aarc-community.org/>

¹¹⁶ <https://elixir-europe.org>

¹¹⁷ <https://www.bbmri-eric.eu/>

¹¹⁸ <https://instruct-eric.org/>

¹¹⁹ <https://www.eosc-life.eu/>

Science Login¹²⁰ service on behalf of 13 Life Science Research Infrastructures, which provides advanced features for identity and access management for sensitive data and is compatible with the EOSC Federation.

- **Common data quality approach:** a common data quality framework, such as EHDS Data Quality Framework proposed in TEHDAS project and the Data Quality and Utility Label included in the EHDS regulation, being discussed in the QUANTUM project, might serve to raise data quality standards in both ecosystems, not just in the health space.
- **Connectivity harmonisation:** EOSC Federation connectors for the Federating services and EHDS national/European connectors development might learn from each other. Any shared components must fully comply with the EHDS security and governance requirements.

5 Data Processing

5.1 Existing landscape

Historically, data processing often occurred in systems provided by individual researchers, necessitating a high degree of data mobilisation, and compliance with one of the legal bases under the GDPR Articles 6 and 9 (such as scientific research in the public interest) with appropriate safeguards as per Article 89. These SPEs are mandated to adhere to stringent requirements to ensure data protection and research integrity. Specifically, the EHDS Regulation stipulates that SPEs must:

- **Ensure strong access controls and security safeguards:** This involves robust authentication mechanisms, granular access permissions, and comprehensive security protocols to protect sensitive health data from unauthorised access or breaches.
- **Prevent data downloads or unauthorised transfers:** A key principle of SPEs is to keep the data within the secure environment, preventing its exfiltration or transfer to unapproved systems. This minimizes the risk of data compromise.
- **Encourage use of well-known software and traceable analytics:** Implementation of well-known software with well-understood data privacy risk management in SPEs streamlines implementation of security and disclosure measures. However, in justified cases implementation of bespoke software has to be permitted in order to allow advanced research purposes; as a consequence, security and disclosure measures might be more challenging in this case. In any case, research methodologies must be traceable and as reproducible as possible. This ensures the reliability and validity of research findings.
- **Maintain audit logs and processing transparency:** To ensure accountability and oversight, SPEs are required to maintain detailed audit trails of all data processing activities. This transparency is crucial for regulatory compliance and public trust.

The development of these SPE requirements is an ongoing collaborative effort, with TEHDAS2 the project tasked with gathering input from all member states and other stakeholders to inform the EC on the final SPE implementation acts. It's important to note that the project focuses on defining the requirements rather than providing the technical solutions themselves. The concept of federated analysis, where data

¹²⁰ <https://lifescience-ri.eu/ls-login/>

remains in its original location and analysis is performed remotely, is increasingly recognised as a key strategy, particularly when data cannot be moved due to its sensitivity or volume, but it is still not clear how the federated analysis will be implemented in EHDS' SPEs. Furthermore, the large data sources may not be colocated with large processing capacities, e.g. hospitals may not have massive GPU infrastructures needed for advanced AI purposes, yet they may be sources of petabytes of data in many fields including omics and imaging technologies. There is still therefore an issue of data mobilisation between data sources and SPEs.

The EOSC community typically addresses non-sensitive data though there are significant exceptions in the life sciences or, e.g. commercial in confidence research. In the e-infrastructures, the EGI-ACE project¹²¹, the PHIRI project¹²² use case solutions were ported to the EGI cloud, but no actual data was processed without the appropriate SPE environment. In the current implementation of the EOSC EU Node, there is no support for processing sensitive (personal) data. But as a part of the Federation of other EOSC Nodes, the use cases working on processing sensitive data are already underway thanks to available data sources (e.g., BBMRI node) and secure processing capacities described in the EOSC ENTRUST project and Life Sciences Connect thematic Node¹²³ (comprising ELIXIR, EMBL, Instruct-ERIC and Euro-Bioimaging) or in the national EOSC Nodes operated by e.g. Italy (ICSC/INFN) and the Netherlands (SURF).

An obvious focus of EOSC aligned sensitive data processing relies on the development and support of federated cross-disciplinary research involving sensitive data within Trusted Research Environments (TREs). While serving a similar purpose to EHDS' SPEs, and in some cases able to host SPEs, EOSC TREs may differ in their implementation, certification processes, and software governance depending on a wide range of research purposes across the scientific domains. Awarded in a Horizon Europe topic included in the 2023 Work Programme, three INFRAEOSC projects are pursuing the development of EOSC TREs in more detail:

- EOSC-ENTRUST¹²⁴: This project aims to create a European network of Trusted Research Environments (TREs) for sensitive data and drive European interoperability by the joint development of a common blueprint for federated data access and analysis. It brings together providers of operational TREs from 15 European countries with a shared goal to implement, validate and promote their capabilities through a common European framework using shared standards and common legal, operational and technical language. This blueprint for interoperability is anchored in the EOSC Interoperability Framework spanning the four dimensions of legal, organisational, technical and semantic interoperability. It further extends the Life Science AAI to Authentication, Authorization, and Accounting Infrastructure (AAAI), and provides a demonstrator of federated analysis and a catalogue of available TRE Providers and their capabilities.
- SIESTA¹²⁵ (Secure Interactive Environments for SensiTiVe data Analytics): This project aims to design and build solutions for secure environments specifically for sensitive data analytics within the EOSC ecosystem. SIESTA envisions a suite of cloud-based tools, services, and methodologies

¹²¹ <https://www.egi.eu/project/egi-ace/>

¹²² <https://www.phiri.eu/>

¹²³ <https://eosc.eu/building-the-eosc-federation/eosc-node-life-sciences-connect>

¹²⁴ <https://eosc-entrust.eu/>

¹²⁵ <https://eosc-siesta.eu/>

to facilitate the effective sharing and processing of sensitive data, with a focus on reproducible environments and state-of-the-art anonymisation techniques.

- TITAN¹²⁶ (Trusted environments for confidential computing and secure data sharing): TITAN proposes to develop secure and trustworthy confidential data processing and sharing capabilities, demonstrating them within the EOSC. The project emphasises adherence to FAIR data principles and open science, with a significant focus on privacy preservation and AI technological solutions aligned with EU ethical, regulatory, and legal frameworks. Its open-source software platform is particularly geared towards government and healthcare use cases.

The EOSC-RAISE project aims to provide the mechanisms for a distributed crowdsourced data processing system, moving from open data to data open for processing, and has also developed data visiting solutions specifically for sensitive data.

These projects, while inspired by many of the same principles, do not imply EHDS regulatory compliance, but their solutions may serve to inform future guidance or interoperability work for regulatory instruments.

A wider set of related secure and/or federated data processing initiatives complement the EHDS by developing domain-specific frameworks for secure, federated data analysis. While operating outside the EHDS legal framework, they contribute valuable technical and semantic experience for its implementation. The most prominent ones are the following:

- 1+ Million Genomes (1+MG): This initiative supports cross-border federated analysis of genomic data, incarnated under the Genomics Data Infrastructure (GDI).¹²⁷
- European federation for cancer images data (EUCAIM): EUCAIM aims to enable federated image data processing across cancer centers, with the BreastScan¹²⁸ project being one of the first large use cases.
- BBMRI-ERIC Federated Platform¹²⁹ comprising Locator and Finder, with privacy-preserving federated data discovery, querying and analysis capabilities. In the domain of cohorts, The DataSHIELD-based aggregated analytical environment^{130,131} is used.
- Other European ESFRI Research Infrastructures (BBMRI, ELIXIR, ECRIN): These infrastructures are coordinating and developing tools to support secure data processing within biobanking, bioinformatics, and clinical trials, respectively.
- EBRAINS Medical Informatics Platform¹³² implementing privacy-preserving data querying and analysis in the domain of mental health and disorders.

¹²⁶ <https://titan-eosc.eu/>

¹²⁷ <https://gdi.onemilliongenomes.eu/>

¹²⁸ <https://www.eibir.org/projects/breastscan/>

¹²⁹ <https://www.bbmri-eric.eu/bbmri-sample-and-data-portal/>

¹³⁰ <https://datashield.org/>

¹³¹ Wolfson, Michael, Susan E. Wallace, Nicholas Masca, Geoff Rowe, Nuala A. Sheehan, Vincent Ferretti, Philippe LaFlamme et al. "DataSHIELD: resolving a conflict in contemporary bioscience—performing a pooled analysis of individual-level data without sharing the data." *International journal of epidemiology* 39, no. 5 (2010): 1372-1382.

¹³² <https://mip.ebrains.eu/>

- Standard Architecture for Trusted Research Environment (SATRE)¹³³ is a TRE blueprint designed in the UK. The SATRE architecture serves as the core element in the federated analysis architecture developed in the DARE UK¹³⁴ project. Conceptually, SATRE specification assesses if a Virtual Research Environment is compliant with TRE notion, and DARE UK defined the architectural model to federate TREs. It is a member and leading contributor to the EOSC ENTRUST project described previously.
- The Research Data Alliance (RDA) has recently endorsed a Working Group on Trusted Research Environments for Sensitive or Confidential Data: FAIRness for Controlled Data and Processes, which focuses on blueprints, interoperability, and risk management. EOSC funded project participants are included.

It's worth noting that under the Digital Decade Policy Programme¹³⁵, certain initiatives are expected to apply to become a European Digital Infrastructure Consortium (EDIC)¹³⁶. This could include the examples of the Genome EDIC (derived from the GDI project) and EUCAIM itself.

Despite these advances, and that several of these initiatives may be in early stages of development, a substantial portion of researchers' data processing still occurs within generic e-Infrastructures, institutional infrastructures, or even on researchers' own devices. Numerous research projects involving health data often develop their own dedicated data processing solutions, tailored to a single project. These environments are built according to the security principles and criteria of the specific project or institution offering the infrastructure. European e-infrastructures and national service providers also play a role in building and supporting these environments.

The integration of Artificial Intelligence (AI) applications, models, and processes is becoming increasingly common within health data processing environments. Projects like RI-SCALE¹³⁷ co-host scientific data with preconfigured AI frameworks and models on compute resources, aiming to unlock the full potential of data and AI for scientific users, research infrastructures, and industry. EOSC Nodes and AI Factories are also integral components of the evolving health data processing landscape.

Across all these infrastructures and initiatives, it is paramount to ensure clear definitions of data controllers and processors, in adherence to the accountability principle of the GDPR. Federated data processing must strictly observe the principles of purpose limitation and data minimisation, guaranteeing that only data essential for specific research objectives is accessed. Furthermore, data subject rights—including access, rectification, and objection—must be respected or lawfully limited where applicable, with unwavering transparency and oversight.

5.2 Gap Analysis, redundancies and opportunities

Within the data processing context, the the specification of SPEs is most critical. In the EHDS regulation, Article 73, which covers such critical infrastructural elements, delegates its final requirements to an upcoming implementing act due by 27 March 2027.¹³⁸ While this is awaited, several communities are

¹³³ <https://satre-specification.readthedocs.io/en/stable>

¹³⁴ <https://dareuk.org.uk/how-we-work/federated-architecture-blueprint>

¹³⁵ <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/europes-digital-decade>

¹³⁶ <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/edic>

¹³⁷ <https://www.egi.eu/project/ri-scale/>

¹³⁸ EHDS, Art.73 §5

developing their own concepts to anticipate the final form of such implementing and delegated acts. This is not a gap *per se*, but a situation that may lead to a possible fragmentation in this ecosystem.

The governance and operational clarity of these systems remain uncertain, particularly from the perspective of service developers who must decide where and how to integrate their services. While recent initiatives such as the Apply AI Strategy and the European Strategy for Artificial Intelligence in Science introduce a high-level governance and architectural vision for AI adoption (for example through AI Factories, AI Gigafactories, RAISE and Experience Centres), their concrete interaction with existing ecosystems such as EOSC Nodes, EHDS secure processing environments, and SIMPL-based European data spaces is still not fully defined. As a result, the growing landscape of concepts and platforms—EOSC Nodes hosting SPEs/TREs, sectoral AI infrastructures under Apply AI, AI Factories and companion Data Labs from the AI in Science Strategy, and the evolution of SIMPL-Open middleware—continues to risk technical and organisational fragmentation. Participants are left with limited guidance on their respective roles and on how these components are expected to interoperate in practice across EOSC, EHDS and the emerging AI infrastructure.

Another specific aspect is the use of federated analyses in the context of EHDS, which allow processing data without pooling. In principle federated analyses are foreseen in principle under EHDS, but their operationalisation will be defined in the implementing act and practical guidance from the EHDS Board. Federated analyses are clearly a major demand in the research communities, especially from those dealing with large, complex datasets where the emphasis now is on moving analysis to the data.

To conclude, the TEHDAS2 Joint Action is gathering and organising the MSs' and communities' visions regarding such requirements and informing the EC towards the writing of the final implementing act. Thus, the EOSC Health Data Task Force should be a major source of information in the consultations opened by this Joint Action, as it gathers the representation of high-profile professionals from major institutions devoted to health data related activities.

5.3 Identified synergies & opportunities

- **Leverage Existing Infrastructure** Experience gained through EOSC's Trusted Research Environments (TREs) can inform the technical design and hosting of EHDS Secure Processing Environments (SPEs). Research infrastructures operating within EOSC provide practical insights that could accelerate the establishment of the SPEs under the EHDS framework, provided all EHDS governance and security requirements are fully met.
- **Align Requirements and Certification:** Once the implementing act on SPEs is adopted, alignment between the certification or assurance schemes for EHDS' SPEs and EOSC's TREs could be explored. A common or interoperable certification framework would simplify compliance for operators active in both ecosystems and promote consistency in security and privacy standards.
- **Build Interoperable European Catalogues:** A coordinated approach could be envisaged to create a federated metadata view—not a merged catalogue—of secure services, tools, and environments across EHDS and EOSC. This would improve discoverability for users while keeping the two legal and governance frameworks distinct.
- **Pilot EHDS Compliance:** existing use cases and drivers within EOSC, such as those in the EOSC-ENTRUST, SIESTA and TITAN projects, could serve to pilot and test EHDS compliance during the

EOSC Federation build up phase. This would provide valuable real-world experience and help refine the EHDS framework.

- **Harness AI Opportunities:** future development should actively integrate the opportunities and address the challenges presented by Artificial Intelligence. The secure data access provided by the EHDS, combined with the computational capacities that will be present in the EOSC and in the AI Factories is essential for advancing AI in healthcare.

